

WAYS TO DEVELOP CREATIVE THINKING IN GEOGRAPHY EDUCATION

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Abstract: This article discusses the importance of creative thinking, the “Six Thinking Hats” method aimed at developing students' ability to analyze problems from various perspectives and enhance their creative thinking, as well as the effectiveness of applying this method in geography lessons. The article analyzes how the method is implemented in the educational process, its role in developing students' thinking abilities, and its methodological aspects.

Keywords: creative thinking, geography, educational process, creative thinking, Edward de Bono, “Six Thinking Hats”, methodology, analytical thinking, new ideas, interactive lessons.

СПОСОБЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ТВОРЧЕСКОГО МЫШЛЕНИЯ В ГЕОГРАФИЧЕСКОМ ОБРАЗОВАНИИ

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются важность креативного мышления, методика “Шесть шляп мышления” для развития творческого подхода и всестороннего анализа проблем учащимися, а также эффективность применения данного метода на уроках географии. В статье проанализированы аспекты внедрения данного метода в образовательный процесс, его роль в развитии мышления учащихся и методические особенности.

Ключевые слова: креативное мышление, география, образовательный процесс, творческое мышление, Эдвард де Боно, “Шесть шляп мышления”, методика, аналитическое мышление, новые идеи, интерактивные уроки

INTRODUCTION

One of the main goals of the educational process is not only to transfer knowledge but also to develop independent thinking and a creative approach in students. In the process of teaching geography, effective methods for fostering creative thinking help students generate new ideas, solve problems creatively, and broaden their worldview. Creative thinking is the ability to innovate, find unique solutions to existing problems, and process ideas in an original way. Geography teachers should not be limited to providing subject-related information but should also focus on developing students' logical and creative thinking. This, in turn, helps shape a comprehensive, multidisciplinary approach among students. Moreover, creative thinking allows students to examine topics from different perspectives, understand interconnections, and apply innovative ways of thinking in problem-solving.

Effective methods for developing creative thinking in the teaching of geography encourage students not only to acquire geographical knowledge but also to engage in analytical and creative thinking. Problem-solving, discussions, project work, interactive games, visualization techniques, and research methods motivate students to apply their knowledge in practice and generate new ideas.

The impact of creative thinking undeniably stands behind significant types of innovation throughout society. However, it is also a universal and equalizing phenomenon, meaning that every individual, to some extent, possesses the ability to think creatively [1].

Creative thinking involves considering an issue from multiple perspectives and approaching a single point from various angles [3].

Developing creative thinking skills in students enables them to solve increasingly complex local and global problems through unconventional approaches [2].

MAIN PART

The 'Six Thinking Hats' method, developed by Edward de Bono, is an innovative methodology designed to effectively manage the thinking process and facilitate viewing issues from multiple perspectives. This method ensures a positive and efficient approach to exploring different viewpoints and solving problems. The primary goal of the 'Six Thinking Hats' technique is to analyze issues comprehensively and encourage creative thinking [4].

Edward de Bono introduced the 'Six Thinking Hats' method in 1985 in his book Six Thinking Hats. This method is based on managing thinking through different approaches and implementing each thinking style separately and distinctly. Each hat represents a specific way of thinking, and they are used simultaneously, which expands the thought process.

1-tab. The "Six Thinking Hats" method expresses each "hat" as a separate approach to thinking:

Hat Color	Type of thinking	Purpose	Example questions
White	Information and facts	The white hat focuses on existing information and facts. The person wearing this hat only deals with concrete and reliable facts when analyzing a problem. This thinking method ensures objectivity and helps avoid false or ambiguous information.	What statistics are available?
Red	Feelings and intuitions	The red hat represents feelings and intuitions. The person wearing this hat examines the emotional aspects of the problem or situation. This is allowed because, in many cases, decisions are not made purely based on logic or facts, but also emotions and feelings play an important role.	How do you feel about this?
Black	Negative thoughts, risks	The black hat is used to identify potential risks, problems, and negative aspects. The person wearing this hat analyzes the negative sides, dangers, and potential difficulties of the issue. This method helps prevent problems or minimize negative outcomes.	What problems might arise?
Yellow	Positive thoughts, benefits	This is about seeing the positive sides of the problem and its benefits. The person wearing this hat analyzes the positive aspects of various	What are the advantages of this?

		solutions, as well as thinking about new opportunities and benefits.	
Green	Creative thoughts, creativity	The green hat is used for creative thinking and developing alternatives. The person wearing this hat tries to generate new ideas, innovative solutions, and unique alternatives. The green hat facilitates the thinking process and helps open new paths.	What other methods might exist?
Blue	Managing the process	The blue hat manages the thinking process. The person wearing this hat organizes the thinking, controls when and how each hat is used. The blue hat ensures a systematic approach and monitors the effectiveness of the thinking process.	What are the next steps?

The methodology for applying this method in the classroom is as follows: students are divided into groups, and each group is given several hats. Each group wears their assigned hats, studies the topic, and gathers their thoughts as a group. Group members prepare their opinions for 10-15 minutes and then present the results to others. At the end of the lesson, students are asked to summarize the ideas expressed under all the hats. At the conclusion of the lesson, it is important to gather feedback from the students, discuss what changes could be made, and have a conversation about how the learned methods can be applied in daily life.

In geography lessons, the "Six Thinking Hats" method provides students the opportunity to analyze a problem from multiple angles and approach geographic topics in a comprehensive manner. For example, when studying the topic of "Urbanization and the Development of Cities," this method can be used effectively. It can be implemented as follows:

White hat (information and facts): Relevant statistical data and facts about the development of cities and the urbanization process are presented. Students discuss topics such as the growth in the number of cities, population density, and the expansion of infrastructure.

Red hat (feelings and intuitions): Students can be asked how they feel about the development of cities and the process of urbanization. For example, the expansion of cities and the increase in population density may cause concern for some students, while others may support it for economic growth.

Black hat (negative aspects and risks): The negative aspects of urbanization, such as environmental pollution, overconsumption of natural resources, and the population facing social inequalities, are discussed.

Yellow hat (positive aspects and benefits): The positive aspects of the development of cities and the urbanization process are highlighted, such as economic growth, the creation of new jobs, the improvement of infrastructure, and the increase in people's quality of life.

Green hat (creative ideas and alternatives): Creative ideas are developed to minimize the negative impacts of urbanization. For example, proposals are made to increase green zones, establish eco-friendly transportation systems, use energy efficiently, and promote sustainable city development.

Blue hat (managing the thinking process): Each group organizes their thoughts and selects the best solutions. For example, general conclusions are drawn about which methods should be applied in city development and how existing problems can be solved.

With the help of this method, students analyze the topic of "Urbanization and the Development of Cities" from all perspectives, considering both the positive and negative aspects. By explaining their opinions, discussing issues, and developing creative solutions, they ensure that the lesson is interactive and effective.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, developing creative thinking in geography education is an essential component of the teaching process and plays a significant role in shaping students' analytical and creative approaches. Creative thinking gives students the opportunity to broaden their worldview, approach problems from different perspectives, and develop new ideas. The application of the "Six Thinking Hats" method in geography lessons helps students analyze the topic from all angles, engage in thoughtful discussion, and come up with innovative solutions. This method provides students the opportunity to manage the thinking process in various directions, consider problems from multiple perspectives, and exchange ideas with one another.

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